

**THE EFFECT OF LEARNING ORGANIZATIONS,
ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION THROUGH WORK ENVIRONMENT
AS A MODERATING VARIABLE ON THE JOB SATISFACTION
OF TEMPORARY EMPLOYEES' (NON MEDICAL) IN THE
ADMINISTRATION SERVICE OF NORTH SUMATRA
UNIVERSITY HOSPITAL MEDAN, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

This study examines the job satisfaction of temporary (non-medical) employees in the administration services at the North Sumatra University Hospital, Medan. This study aims to determine and analyze the influence of organizational learning, achievement motivation on job satisfaction, and whether the work environment can moderate the relationship between organizational learning and achievement motivation towards work satisfaction of temporary (non-medical) employees in the administration services at the North Sumatra University Hospital Medan. Quantitative descriptive was employed as data analysis method. The population of this study was 82 temporary (non-medical) employees in the administrative division of North Sumatra University Hospital who have worked for at least one year and have participated in several trainings at the North Sumatra University Hospital. The technique of determining the sample used is the census method. Methods of collecting data with questionnaires The results of this study show partially (t test) shows that organizational learning and achievement motivation have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, simultaneously (F-test) learning organization and achievement motivation have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Moderation testing with a residual test approach, the work environment is not able to moderate (strengthen) the relationship between learning organizations to job satisfaction.

Keywords: organizational learning, achievement motivation, job satisfaction, work environment

1. Introduction

Human resources is one of the determinants of the success of the company because the role of human resources as a valuable asset is to plan, implement and control various operational activities of the company. Companies need to view employees as individuals who have needs for recognition, appreciation, and not as tools for achieving company goals. Job satisfaction has an important meaning in every organization, because job satisfaction is a criterion for measuring organizational success in meeting the needs of members who are in it. Job satisfaction is something that is very personal, where one can feel only the person concerned and has nature which is not always the same between people or one another (Riansari et al., 2012).

One of the elements that must be considered in human resource management in an organization is the job satisfaction of employees. Job satisfaction and high employee capacity development are certainly highly expected by the North Sumatra University Hospital because it encourages the advancement and development of hospitals. The ability to develop themselves and increase employee job satisfaction will improve the quality of work and the performance of employees who will improve the quality and performance of hospitals and be able to provide excellent service and in accordance with the vision, mission and goals of the hospital.

The North Sumatra University Hospital must also be able to guarantee that all existing systems will strengthen the values of learning organizations, even though the organization is always changing through new employees and promotions, but the core of learning organizations will always be presented. According to the results of research conducted by Tumbel, Liando and Rumawas (2015) and Diharjo (2017), the learning organization has a significant effect on job satisfaction.

The first factor that is deemed to play a role in determining job satisfaction is the learning organization. Learning organization is the process of organizational members facing a problem, identifying alternative solutions by using values, norms, choosing and implementing one of the best alternatives, and evaluating the results. This is also inseparable from the existence of the organization itself, in other words the learning organization that is woven into a company will have an impact on employee job satisfaction which in the end will give an increase in the performance of the employees concerned.

The second factor that is believed to play a role in determining job satisfaction is achievement motivation. Ardana, et al (2012) argued that "*Motivation is a force that encourages a person to carry out an action which is in essence exists internally and externally that can be positive or negative. This is dependable on the manager's toughness.*" Companies provide good achievement motivation in the form of material and non-material and

internal and external, so employees are expected to be able to complete all the tasks and authority of the work that has been given by the leadership. The task for the leadership is also to provide motivation for achievement which can later improve employee work's motivation.

The North Sumatra University Hospital must increase achievement motivation so that employees are expected to be able to complete all tasks and authority given by the leaders/ superiors. And the North Sumatra University Hospital has determined to build a work climate that is safe and professionally satisfying for its employees. Employee satisfaction will arise if employees feel safe, comfortable, and satisfied with their work environment. The establishment of a work environment that supports work performance will lead to satisfaction for employees in an organization, so that employees will survive in the company and become an important asset for the company.

Work Environment is considered as a moderating variable. Based on the opinions of previous researchers, the work environment is a portrayal of the reality in the dynamic world of work. The workplace can provide information about the day to day life of employees who come to work, assemble for the same purpose, carry out their work, and live in organizational rules and regulations framework. Job satisfaction of employees in the company is said to be high if employees easily get the information they need to do work and be comfortable with the state of affairs around their work environment. Most of the good work environment can help improve job satisfaction and a positive relationship between work environment and job satisfaction exist for all types of work groups, but the physical and non-physical environment are factors that influence job satisfaction in addition to compensation, promotion and characteristics of the work.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Learning Organizations

Learning Organizations can be interpreted as an organization that continuously strives to develop capabilities in a changing environment (Robbins, 2008). Learning organizations are also deemed as organizations that are able to develop the ability to continually adjust and change (Wahyudi, 2009). Organizational learning is a situation where the company realizes the importance of training and development related to sustainable performance and takes appropriate action (Mondy, 2008: 211). The organizations can learn and change based on what is learned by each worker in the organization (Ortenblad, 2013). Based on the above definition, it can be concluded that learning organization is an organizational condition that gives the opportunity for all members of the organization to learn to continually face problems, in order to improve their ability to identify.

There are five disciplines for the creation of learning organizations (Senge, 2006), namely:

- 1) System thinking;
- 2) Personal expertise;
- 3) Mental model;
- 4) Building a shared vision;
- 5) Team learning.

Organizations at the North Sumatra University Hospital conduct learning organizations, the criteria are:

- 1) A comparative study which aim is to develop a better hospital;
- 2) Participate in training held by the North Sumatra University Hospital;
- 3) Attend seminars in accordance with the field of employees;
- 4) Follow and hold regular Education and Training (*Diklat*).

2.2 Achievement Motivation

Achievement motivation is a psychological process that evokes and leads to behaviors towards achieving goals or goal directed behavior (Wibowo, 2010). Managers need to understand this psychological process if they want to succeed in building work towards the completion of organizational goals. Achievement motivation is also assumed as "*The whole process of giving motivation works to subordinates in such a way that they want to work sincerely in order to achieve organizational goals efficiently and economically*" (Siagian and Sedarmayanti, 2011: 233).

Based on the aforementioned definition of achievement motivation, there is a strong impetus for employees to achieve success in carrying out optimal work in competition which results in the form of achievements for themselves. The desire to excel will increase motivation so that the employee will finish the job better.

Some characteristic characteristics of highly motivated employees (Mangkunegara, 2013) are:

- 1) They take advantage of feedback,
- 2) They usually have a comprehensive work plan,
- 3) Having goals that are easily achieved,
- 4) Dare to take and take risks,
- 5) Have high personal responsibility, and
- 6) They usually look for opportunities to realize a predetermined plan.

The characteristics of good motivated individuals (Mangkunegara, 2013) are as follows:

- 1) Doing difficult work with satisfying results,
- 2) Do something better than someone else,
- 3) Do something to achieve success,
- 4) Do something as decent as possible,
- 5) Do something very meaningful,

- 6) Desiring to be an expert person or master a certain field, and
- 7) Complete tasks that require the effort and skills they have.

According to Juliani in Dalimunthe (2008), if you want to motivate people at work, Herzberg suggests emphasizing things related to work itself or the results such as opportunities for promotion, opportunities for personal growth, recognition, responsibility and achievement.

2.3 Work Environment

The work environment is the whole work facilities and infrastructure that are around employees who are doing work that can affect the implementation of work (Sutrisno, 2009). This work environment includes workplaces, facilities and tools for work, cleanliness, lighting, tranquility, including work relations between people in the place.

The work environment is the entire tooling and materials faced. The environment around the employee in work, the method of work, and the work arrangements both as individuals and as a group (Sedarmayanti, 2009). Based on some of the above meanings, the work environment is a condition around the workplace both physically and non-physically which can give the impression of pleasant, secure, reassuring employees that can affect employees in carrying out their duties.

The work environment (Sedarmayanti, 2011) is divided into two, namely:

- 1) Physical Work Environment is all physical conditions found around the workplace that can affect employees either directly or indirectly, for example (air temperature, air source, adequate company facilities, work tools, and the availability of safety devices).
- 2) The Non-Physical Work Environment is all the conditions that occur related to work relations, both relationships with superiors and fellow colleagues, or relationships with subordinates, for example the relationship of communication between superiors to subordinates, among fellow employees, and between subordinates to superiors.

Hospitals, in assigning duties and responsibilities to employees, should also pay attention to the work environment perceived by employees. According to Bachtiar (2012), "*Companies are required to be able to provide a sense of security and comfort for employees at work*". The condition of a good and healthy work environment in the organization will make employees feel motivated to work harder, composed and focus on working on the tasks given will have an impact on increasing motivation and generating employee job satisfaction. The condition of a pleasant work environment is very important as an incentive for employee job satisfaction in carrying out their work.

2.4 Job Satisfaction

Hasibuan (2014) argues that job satisfaction is an emotional attitude when one feels passionate about the job. This attitude is reflected by work morale, discipline, and work

performance. Whereas according to Siagian (2012) job satisfaction is a way of looking at someone both positive and negative about their work.

Based on the above understanding, job satisfaction is a reflection of the employee's feelings towards his employment. This can be seen in the employee's positive attitude towards the work and his environment. Instead, employees who are dissatisfied will be negative towards work in different forms. The existence of employee job dissatisfaction should be detected by the organization.

Ardana et al (2012) explained that the theory underlying the concept of job satisfaction is the Two factor Theory proposed by Frederick Herzberg, states that there are two factors that can cause employees to be satisfied or dissatisfied, namely:

- 1) The satisfier factor or "motivator". Factors as job satisfaction consisting of encouragement achievement, recognition, progress, work itself, opportunities to develop and responsibility.
- 2) Dissociation factor or "hygiene" (maintenance).

Maintenance factors or called *dissatisfiers* include administration and company policy, quality of supervision, relations with supervisors, salary or compensation, relationships with other employees, working environment conditions, work security and status.

According to Syahreza, Lumbanraja, Dalimunthe and Yeni (2017) Compensation has a high effect on employee retention within a company with satisfactory compensation, employees will feel that the company is caring about employee needs. Employee satisfaction will be shown by the employees at the company or retention.

According to Herzberg's research (2014), there are three important things that must be considered in influencing employee job satisfaction, including the following:

- 1) The things that encourage employees are challenging jobs that include feelings of achievement, responsibility, progress, enjoyment, and the recognition of everything.
- 2) Matters that disappoint employees are mainly underestimated factors in employment, work regulations, information, recess time, designation of title, rights, salary, allowances, etc.
- 3) Employees will be disappointed if opportunities for achievement are limited. They will become sensitive to their environment and start looking for mistakes.

Robbins (2017) states there are four ways employees express their dissatisfaction, namely as follows:

- 1) Exit, which is leaving work including looking for another job.
- 2) Voicing out which is actively giving suggestions for improvement and discussing problems with superiors to improve conditions.
- 3) Neglecting which is passively allowing conditions to be worse, such as frequent absences, late work, lack of effort, and often making mistakes.

- 4) Loyalty, which is optimistically waiting for improved conditions, including defending organizations when faced with external condemnation and trusting organizations and management to "do the right thing".

3. Research Methods

This type of research is quantitative descriptive. The population in this study was 82 temporary (non-medical) employees at the North Sumatra University Hospital who have worked for at least one year and have participated in several trainings at the North Sumatra University Hospital. In this study, researchers used census samples because the population was less than 100 respondents. The total samples examined in this study were eighty-two temporary (non-medical) employees at the North Sumatra University Hospital in Medan.

The multiple linear regression analysis carried out in this study is multiple regression analysis using the SPSS calculation tool. This study used a residual test because the interaction test and absolute difference test have a tendency to have high multicollinearity between independent variables and this will violate the classic assumption in Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression (Ghozali, 2013). To overcome this multicollinearity, another method was developed called a residual test.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

The multiple linear regression formula:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$$

Description:

Y = Job Satisfaction;

a = Constant;

b₁, b₂ = Coefficient;

X₁ = Learning Organization;

X₂ = Achievement motivation.

Table 1: Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,960	3,261		1,214	,228
	Learning Organization	,496	,117	,496	4,223	,000
	Achievement Motivation	,369	,123	,353	3,006	,004

Dependent Variables: Employees' Job Satisfaction

Source: Primary data processed, 2019.

From the table above, the regression equation formed from this test is:

$$Y = 3.960 + 0.496 X1 + 0.369 X2 + e$$

The above equation can be interpreted as follows:

- 1) The constant value (α) = 3.960 shows if the learning organization variable (X1) and achievement motivation (X2) = 0, then job satisfaction = 3.960.
- 2) Value of Variable X1 (Learning Organization) of 0.496 means that Learning Organization variables contribute positively in influencing job satisfaction which is equal to 0.496 or 49.6%. This means that if Learning Organizations increase by multiples of 1 x then it will affect job satisfaction, which also increases by 49.6%, and vice versa.
- 3) X2 Variable Value (Achievement Motivation) of 0.369 means that the Achievement Motivation variable contributes positively in influencing job satisfaction which is equal to 0.369 or 36.9%. This means that if Achievement Motivation increases by a multiple of 1 x, it will affect job satisfaction, which will increase by 36.9%, and vice versa.

Based on the results of partial testing (t test) from the table above it can be concluded as follows:

- 1) Learning organization variables have a value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ where $4,223 > 1,664$ with a significance level of $0,000 < 0,05$ so that it can be stated that organizational learning has a significant effect on job satisfaction.
- 2) Variable achievement motivation has a $t_{count} > t_{table}$ where $3,006 > 1,664$ with a significance level of $0.015 < 0.05$ so that it can be stated that achievement motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction.

The coefficient of determination can be seen in the adjusted R square column, which is shown in the following table:

Table 2: Determination Coefficient Test Results

Summary^b model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
1	,813 ^a	,662	,653

Dependent Variables: Employees' Job Satisfaction

Source: Primary data processed, 2019

Based on Table 4.29, it shows the Adjusted R Square value of 0.653 or 65.3%, this indicates that the variable job satisfaction can be explained by organizational learning variables and achievement motivation is equal to 65.3%, while the remaining 34.7% is explained by other factors not included in this research model.

4.2 Moderating Variable Test Results

Ghozali (2013) states that there are three ways to test regression with verbal moderation, namely: (1) interaction test, (2) absolute difference test, and (3) residual test. In this study used a residual test. The residual test is used because the interaction test and absolute difference test tend to have high multicollinearity between independent variables and this will violate the classic assumption in ordinary least square (OLS) regression (Ghozali, 2013). To overcome this multicollinearity, another method was developed called a residual test.

Table 3: Test of Significance of Work environment in Moderating Relationship between learning organization (X1) and achievement motivation (X2) on job satisfaction (Residual Test)

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	37,717	1,037		36,368	,000
	abs_res_xz1	,114	,406	,041	,281	,779
	abs_res_xz2	,349	,371	,136	,942	,349

Source: Data processed (2019).

In testing moderation with a residual test approach, a variable is said to moderate the independent variables if the regression coefficients of the independent variables are negative and significant (Ghozali, 2013: 244). Note that the regression coefficient of job satisfaction is positive and not significant. This means that the work environment variable cannot moderate the relationship between organizational learning and achievement motivation on job satisfaction (Residual Test). The following is a picture of the results of this study.

Figure 1: Result of the Study

4.3 Discussion

4.3.1 Learning Organization has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Based on the partial test (t test), learning organization has a significant positive effect on job's satisfaction. This means that the more the North Sumatra University Hospital develops learning organizations, the more job satisfaction increases, the more satisfied and ultimately it will improve optimal performance. This is based on descriptive statistical analysis and analysis of the characteristics of respondents. In organizations, each employee continually expands their ability to deliver work results as they wish and aspire, where innovative and expansive thinking patterns are grown, collective aspirations are freed and all employees are continuously doing cooperative learning.

When the North Sumatra University Hospital grows, leaders must be able to guarantee that all existing learning systems will strengthen cultural values, even though the North Sumatra University Hospital is always changing (through new employees and promotions), but the core of the learning organization will be always remain solid within the hospital. With the existence of learning organizations, employees can exchange ideas, share opinions and information about improving the quality of work and resolve everything that has to do with their work. In this way, the policies given by the leadership in the work environment, learning organizations will increase the work satisfaction of the company's employee's particularly in the long term. According to the results of research conducted by Dekolou and Trivellas (2015); Rose et al. (2009);

Nyukorong (2016); Tumbel et al. (2015); and Diharjo (2017) show that organizational learning has a significant influence on job satisfaction.

4.3.2 Achievement motivation has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction

Achievement motivation has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction. The reason is because the respondents already have intelligence and personal maturity. It can be said that the better the motivation given to employees, the job satisfaction of employees will increase. So that motivation is needed by an organization to increase employee satisfaction because this will encourage employees to work optimally and the purpose of the North Sumatra University Hospital will be achieved. Employees who aspire to compete and outperform other employees basically have high achievement motivation. Examples of achievement motivation at the North Sumatra University Hospital is in the form of getting a promotion, increasing quality in medical services obtained, and performance benefits impact on employee job satisfaction. Employees with high achievement motivation generally set targets for achievement higher than what they can come to be. This causes the employee to always be oriented to success in carrying out his work. This condition is indicated by the high level of employee job satisfaction, especially related to the work itself. The higher employee achievement motivation will increase work satisfaction. Another point about high achievement motivation is that the employee always aspires changes.

The results of the study conducted by Hussain et al. (2010); Mohan and Ajina (2015); Sohail et al (2014); Noor (2012); Sukarman (2014); Nofendra (2015); Oktavianti (2016) and Rahdita et al (2015) show that motivation has a significant effect on job satisfaction.

4.3.3 Effect of Learning Organizations and Achievement Motivation on Job Satisfaction

Organizational learning and positive achievement motivation simultaneously have a significant effect on job satisfaction. This means that in organizations, everyone continually expands their ability to produce results in such a way as they expect and aspire, where innovative and expansive thinking patterns are grown, collective aspirations are freed and everyone continues to learn together. Learning systems that are continuously carried out through work-solving problems can be done in groups, as well as exchanging ideas. Then it needs to be maintained by always providing learning opportunities for employees to learn to solve problems both individually and in groups. When the North Sumatra University Hospital grows, leaders must be able to guarantee that all existing systems will strengthen cultural values, even though the organization is always changing (through new employees and promotions), but the core of learning organizations will always be remaining alive. With the existence of learning organizations, employees can exchange ideas, opinions and information about improving the quality of work and resolve everything that has to do with their work.

With this way policies given by the leadership in the work environment, learning organizations will increase the work satisfaction of company employees in the long term.

Examples of achievement motivation at the North Sumatra University Hospital, for example job promotion, year-end bonuses, increase in medical services and performance benefits which have an impact on employee job satisfaction. This condition is indicated by the high level of employee job satisfaction, especially related to the work itself. The higher employee achievement motivation will increase employee satisfaction. With the existence of learning organizations and achievement motivation, it will encourage employees to achieve success in their work, namely by carrying out their duties optimally in competition, which in the end will be an achievement for them. The higher employee achievement motivation will increase employee satisfaction. Results of research conducted by Marlikan (2011); and Sareen and Joshi (2016) also show that learning and motivation organizations have a positive influence on improving employee performance, so that ultimately it can affect job satisfaction perceived by employees.

4.3.4 The work environment does not moderate the relationship between Learning Organizations and achievement motivation towards Job Satisfaction

This means that the work environment variable does not moderate the relationship between organizational learning and achievement motivation towards job satisfaction (Residual Test) because:

- 1) Non-medical temporary staff at the North Sumatra University Hospital performs services to patients. Regardless the comfortable working conditions, the staff of the University of North Sumatra Hospital must continue to work and provide the best service to patients. For example if there is damage to the Registration system from the BPJS, they must still register manually so that patients can be served. Other examples such as air conditioning do not work which will have an impact on the comfort of employees, but employees must continue to do their jobs.
- 2) If there are too many queues of patients, especially every Monday and Thursday, the Heart Poly causes the patient to wait too long because the old Medical Record file goes down to registration, so the patient protests to the Public Relation of the North Sumatra University Hospital. Public Relations staffs at the North Sumatra University Hospital still have to provide an explanation to the patient and serve the patient so that the patient can understand and can patiently wait for the queue.
- 3) Non-medical temporary staff of the North Sumatra University Hospital still receives a bonus for the work carried out and does not depend on the number of patients served. This leads to the continuous work of employees to target better quality.

4.4 Limitations

The results of this study have several weaknesses that need consideration, including:

- 1) This study uses a survey method; one of the weaknesses of this method is the possibility of a bias response from the respondents.
- 2) The North Sumatra University Hospital is a new organization so researchers are still limited to conducting research
- 3) Respondents are only limited to temporary (non-medical) employees.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of testing the hypothesis and referring to the formulation and objectives of this study, conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- 1) Partial test results (t-test) show that learning organization variables significantly influence job satisfaction.
- 2) Based on the F-Test, learning organizations and achievement motivation simultaneously have a significant effect on job satisfaction.
- 3) The partial test results (t-Test) show that the variable achievement motivation significantly influences job satisfaction.
- 4) The results of the moderation test with the residual test approach, the work environment cannot moderate the relationship between organizational learning and achievement motivation towards job satisfaction (Residual Test).

5.1 Suggestion

The suggestion that the author can give are:

- 1) It is recommended to the North Sumatra University Hospital to continue encouraging and motivating employees to be able to achieve success in their work that is by carrying out work optimally in competing well which will ultimately be an achievement for the employee. For example, the North Sumatra University Hospital provides bonuses and awards to employees who excel, given the opportunity to develop the ability of employees by sending employees to attend national-scale training; there is certainty for the career path of employees at the North Sumatra University Hospital.
- 2) Based on several limitations contained in this study, to further research it is recommended to be able to obtain a representative sample of the population of a research observation, by carrying out research at the Hospital in North Sumatra.
- 3) The next researcher should be able to expand on other variables. So that further research results are expected to make a more meaningful contribution in increasing the factors that influence job satisfaction.

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